

ENRICH IN AFRICA

D3.2 : Summary Report on Online Materials

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Coordinator:	STEINBEIS 2i GMBH - Germany
Consortium:	IMPACT HUB – Austria EUROPEAN BUSINESS AND INNOVATION CENTRE NETWORK AISBL – Belgium SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVACO – Portugal AGORIZE SAS – France BONDY INNOVATION – France CO-CREATION HUB LIMITED – Nigeria I-HUB LIMITED – Kenya METHYS CONSULTING (PTY) LTD – South Africa TECH ACCELERATOR (PTY) LTD – South Africa SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION POLICY RESEARCH ORGANISATION – Tanzania BPI FRANCE FINANCEMENT SA – France
About EiA:	Funded by the European Union (Horizon 2020 programme), ENRICH in Africa is a project designed to bring together core stakeholders from both regions, in order to support and strengthen the European and African innovation ecosystem.

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Deliverable D3.2 : Summary Report on Online Materials

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public	√
PP	Restricted to other program participants (including the EC services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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Table of Contents

1. Deliverable Summary.....	6
2. Deliverable Results.....	6
3. Continuity and sustainability: content availability for the EiA center	8
4. Appendices.....	9

1. Deliverable Summary

Between M12 and M36 Impact Hub was responsible for creating a Virtual Academy to provide online capacity building opportunities to ENRICH in African Champions, bringing together tools, templates and guides, structured learning journeys, cohort-based virtual groups, and learning forums. This Virtual Academy was designed to offer participating Entrepreneur Support Organisations access to Impact Hubs various tools and methodologies co-created by its global network.

2. Deliverable Results

The central component of the Virtual Academy is an online structured learning journey hosted on Teachable, published December 2021, available to Entrepreneur Support Organisations ever since. Alongside this, cohort-based virtual groups and learning forums were facilitated via Bootcamp Trainings (Task 3.1). [The Virtual Academy can be accessed here.](#)

48 individuals have enrolled into the Virtual Academy, from a total of 19 countries. Anonymised details of users can be found in the Appendix 1.

This learning journey equips participants with foundational knowledge in preparation for upcoming training and Virtual Academy. As participants progress through this curriculum they:

1. Discover best practice, methodologies and tools to use in incubation and acceleration programs.
2. Take action locally, with your team and community to implement learnings in the real world.
3. Develop an approach and vocabulary that aligns with the broader EiA Champion community.

The Virtual Academy consolidates learning and methodologies co-created by entrepreneur support practitioners around the globe, in a variety of media. The curriculum is structured

around the following modules (all sub-modules and content can be viewed by following the link provided above):

1. Getting started
2. Understanding the journey stage of your entrepreneurs
3. Designing an Entrepreneur Support Program
4. Scouting for program participants
5. Selecting the right program participants
6. Delivering the right support through your program
7. Connecting participants to supportive people
8. Facilitating access to capital
9. Measuring, evaluating and learning
10. Scaling Stage support
11. Diversity, Equity and Inclusion
12. Embedding Circularity
13. Moving forwards

In addition to guidance regarding incubation and acceleration service design and delivery, Impact Hub also incorporated guidance on how to integrate inclusion and environmental action into such support, based on feedback and learning from consortium partners. These two modules on the Virtual Academy (modules 11 and 12), provide foundational educational material on diversity and inclusion, as well as circular economy, alongside practical action that can be taken to make progress in these areas within one's organization.

The Virtual Academy was promoted through the various bootcamps and champion gatherings delivered by Impact Hub.

3. Continuity and sustainability: content availability for the EiA center

Pending a licensing agreement to be agreed between Impact Hub and ENRICH in Africa Centre, the materials from the learning journey listed below will be made available to the ENRICH in Africa Centre beyond the timeline of the project. Impact Hub will be making all files falling within the scope of the licensing agreement available on Google Drive. Enrich in Africa Centre will then be able to access these files according to the terms of the licensing agreement. The transition is to be completed by July 2024, with the Teachable course available in the meantime to ensure sustained access.

- [The four journey stages](#)
- [Designing and entrepreneur support program - introduction video](#)
- [Scouting for program participants - introduction video](#)
- [Selecting the right program participants - introduction video](#)
- [Delivering the right support through your program - introduction video](#)
- [Connecting participants to supportive people - introduction video](#)
- [Facilitating access to capital - introduction video](#)
- [Measuring, evaluating and learning - introduction video](#)
- [Scaling Stage support - scaling as a mindset](#)
- [Scaling Stage support - the core element](#)
- [Diversity, Equity and Inclusion - why DEI matters](#)
- [Diversity, Equity and Inclusion - understanding your relationship to power](#)
- [Diversity, Equity and Inclusion - building a culture of inclusion](#)
- [Diversity, Equity and Inclusion - decolonisation in focus](#)
- [Diversity, Equity and Inclusion - environmental justice in focus](#)

4. Appendices

Appendix 1: Enrolments

User Organization	User Country
Bond'innov 1	India
Bond'innov 11	Morocco
Bond'innov 2	Unknown
Bond'innov 3	Senegal
Bond'innov 4	France
Bond'innov 5	Germany
Bond'innov 6	Brussels
Bond'innov 7	France
Bond'innov 8	France
Bond'innov 9	Niger
Bond'innov 10	France
E4Impact	Italy
Edu Spark	India
Fintech Associates	Nigeria
iHub 1	Kenya
iHub 2	Kenya
iHub 3	Kenya
Impact Hub Amsterdam	Netherlands
Impact Hub Dakar	Senegal
Impact Hub Dakar	Senegal
Impact Hub Dar es Salaam 1	Tanzania
Impact Hub Dar es Salaam 2	Tanzania
Impact Hub Dar es Salaam 3	Tanzania
Impact Hub Harare 1	Zimbabwe
Impact Hub Harare 2	Zimbabwe

Impact Hub Harare 3	Zimbabwe
Impact Hub Kathmandu 1	Nepal
Impact Hub Kathmandu 2	Nepal
Impact Hub Lusaka	Zambia
Impact Hub Phnom Penh	Cambodia
Innovation Support Network	Nigeria
JIC	Czechia
Methys	South Africa
Opolo	Unknown
SPICI srl	Italy
Steinbeis 1	Germany
Steinbeis 2	Germany
Steinbeis 3	Germany
Tech Bridge Invest 1	Kenya
Tech Bridge Invest 2	Kenya
University of Tasmania	Australia
Zixtech 1	Cameroon
Zixtech 2	Cameroon

Appendix 2: Visuals

Entrepreneur Support at Start-up, Growth and Scaling Stage

A learning journey for ENRICH in Africa Champions developing and delivering incubation, acceleration and scaling services

START NOW!

Ignite your capacity building journey here

This learning journey designed support you, as an ENRICH in Africa Champion, develop your support for entrepreneurs.

This learning journey will equip you with foundational knowledge in preparation for upcoming training and Virtual Academy. As you progress through this curriculum you will:

1. Discover best practice, methodologies and tools that to use in your incubation and acceleration programs.
2. Take action locally, with your team and community so that you implement learnings in the real world.
3. Develop an approach and vocabulary that aligns you with the broader EIA Champion community.

Africa - EU collaboration

ENRICH
IN AFRICA

Funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 programme and coordinated by Steinbeis Zi in Germany, ENRICH in Africa works with key partners and advisors from the innovation landscape of Europe and Africa. Together we address the needs for capacity development of incubators, accelerators, and entrepreneurs in both regions.

This learning journey has been co-created by entrepreneur support practitioners from around the globe, all part of **Impact Hub**, a network of 24,000+ entrepreneurial impact makers.

The ENRICH in Africa Project has brought together **key actors within the African and European innovation ecosystem** as partners in the development of this exciting initiative.

ENRICH in Africa has received funding from the European Union's **Horizon 2020** research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004709.

What to expect

This learning journey is part of a broader package of support being offered to you through the **Enrich in Africa Virtual Academy**. It is designed to equip you with foundational knowledge before participating in live trainings, cohort-based peer groups and learning forums.

To start, you have access to foundational modules, each focused on a key topic relating to entrepreneur support programs.

1. **Designing** an Entrepreneur Support Program
2. **Scouting** for program participants
3. **Selecting** the right program participants
4. **Delivering** the right support through your program
5. **Connecting** participants to supportive people
6. **Facilitating** access to capital
7. **Measuring**, evaluating and learning

Within each module you will find a range of learning resources developed by program experts from across the Impact Hub Network - webinars, videos, templates, tools and assignments. Facilitators may refer to Impact Hubs at times, but information and insights apply to any organisation that offers entrepreneur support or business development services.

You also have modules relating to how to embed **circular design principles** and **diversity, equity and inclusion** into your work. This is based on Impact Hub's global work in these fields over recent years.

Now, let's get started on the fundamentals!

Complete and Continue >

Introduction

 'Unusual suspects' focus on people with potential, diversity & lived experiences		
 Learning adapt & learn from experience to continually improve		

Complete and Continue >

< Edit in Admin
Preview as admin
You can see both published and unpublished content

Home
Settings
< Previous Lesson
Complete and Continue >

Diversity, equity and inclusion

- Introduction
- Why diversity, equity and inclusion matter (7:25)
- Understanding your relationship to power (6:29)
- Building a culture of learning and inclusion (6:24)
- Decolonisation in focus (15:20)
- Environmental Justice in focus (7:32)

Embedding Circularity

- Introduction
- Customise this page

Why diversity, equity and inclusion matter

Adanma's recommended reading:

- [DEI glossary](#) | The Communications network
- [Funder guide for engaging grantees on DEI \(guide\)](#) | Ford Foundation

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